

Editorial

Scopus' 2024 CiteScore metrics for *Evergreen* are encouraging. The total citations of articles from *Evergreen* between 2021 and 2024 reached 3,600. We published 842 articles last year. That's incredible! These articles represent about 20% of total submissions, yielding an official CiteScore of 4.3 for 2024. Figure 1 shows the CiteScore of *Evergreen* in 2024.

While this matches our 2023 score, we can dig slightly deeper and observe meaningful progress. The SJR improves to 0.391 from 0.376 in 2023. Unfortunately, the SNIP drops to 1.192 from 1.513. We have more good news: *Evergreen* is now included in Engineering (miscellaneous), and the percentile is fantastic—69th. The percentiles for other categories drop slightly, partly because of more journals in those areas. Please see Figure 2 for more details.

One note: Scimago's classification lags behind Scopus data. While we rank in the 69th percentile, Scimago still shows Q3 status and misses our new Engineering category. A journal with a 69th percentile clearly merits better than Q3, but this should update in their next cycle. Interested readers can refer to the Scimago webpage for *Evergreen*.

Fig. 1: CiteScore of *Evergreen* in 2024¹⁾

Fig. 2: The percentile of *Evergreen* from 2017 to 2024²⁾

The metrics from Scopus for *Evergreen* in 2024 strongly suggest steady and significant progress of the journal. We think that the numbers will be even better next year. And we are confident the numbers will be great. We further think that we are in the right direction. The subject areas of *Evergreen* have been social science, materials science, computer science (ML, data, AI) and engineering miscellaneous. We will continue publishing excellent papers from these areas.

We're pleased to publish *Evergreen* Volume 12 Issue 02. This issue consists of regular papers only—8 review articles and 45 research papers addressing the latest developments in science and engineering, both natural and social sciences. We hope readers find insightful analysis and impactful results in this publication.

We'd like to acknowledge the significant contributions of our authors and their interest in publishing with *Evergreen*. As we publish more, the insights and comments of reviewers become indispensable. We strongly appreciate their support and offer eminent authority to reviewers and their decisions. We're thankful to the *Evergreen* management and committee (IGSES and GT Center from Kyushu University). We've been working to simplify the submission process, format requirements, and citation styles for productivity. We hope our efforts will help grow the *Evergreen* community.

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Evergreen - Joint Journal of Novel Carbon Resource Sciences & Green Asia Strategy

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References

- 1) <https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100812868?origin=resultslist#tabs=0>
- 2) <https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100812868&tip=sid&exact=no>